

Cyber Warriors: A Series of Serious Pedagogical Cybersecurity Games for Secondary Schools Students

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Abstract

Cyber attacks can cause substantial damage to companies, key infrastructures and even governments. Therefore, it is important to teach children and students how to protect themselves before going into their working lives. Serious cyber games already exist for this purpose, such as Elevation of Privilege and CyberCIEGE. However, these games do not have a clear mapping between learning objectives and game mechanics. This paper presents four serious cybersecurity games aimed at teaching students from the age of 11 to 18, and are the first to be based on an educational framework produced by the UK government. The games are hosted on a publicly accessible website (<https://cyber-warriors.soton.ac.uk/>). Two studies were also conducted which collected feedback based on the Technology Acceptance Model, to analyse the efficacy of teaching the different security concepts in a gamified way. Three metrics, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness and Intention To Use, were used to evaluate the games, with overall average responses of 4.08, 3.97, and 3.91 respectively. This showed them to be successful and engaging, demonstrating the potential for creating more serious cybersecurity games aimed at students. These were hosted on a website, which could become an open-source platform allowing people to contribute different games also based on other educational frameworks.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, Education, Gamification, Serious Gaming, Security Awareness

1 Introduction

Cybersecurity is a persistent challenge in modern computing. The frequency of cyber-attacks targeting organizations has been increasing yearly with a notable 5.5% rise in the number of organizations falling victim to six or more successful cyber-attacks from 2020 to 2022 [1]. Additionally, the cybersecurity job market has been adversely affected. Organizations are having difficulties finding candidates possessing the appropriate level of technical skill required for advertised job roles [2]. Thus, there is a compelling demand for additional education on cybersecurity. Not only is this education necessary within organizations in general, but specifically within the education sector itself. In 2022, 90.5% of all educational institutions worldwide experienced at least one successful cyber-attack [1]. Within the education sector, adolescents aged 11 to 18 are at risk as they may not understand the potential dangers associated with their digital devices. This vulnerability is intensified by the constantly evolving technological landscape, which is increasingly being integrated into everyday living and educational contexts. Once exposed to a threat, adolescents may

not understand the appropriate actions to take to protect themselves. Therefore, it is important to teach cybersecurity concepts to people within this age range so that they can safeguard themselves and each other online.

Contemporary teaching methods employ standard lessons, which arguably do not highlight the importance of such critical skills. This work makes use of an emerging teaching methodology known as ‘serious games.’ The latter uses gamification principles by applying game mechanics to activities that may be considered mundane [3]. This is becoming increasingly popular with training and teaching as it allows for a sense of enjoyment and achievement to be experienced by the trainee from completing a routine task. Research also shows that gamification is effective even for children as young as those in primary school [4]. Existing cybersecurity games aim to address these vulnerabilities among adolescents by incorporating gamification elements [5] [6]. However, many fall short as they prioritize entertainment aspects over educational aspects. Furthermore, many of these games fail to align the desired skills and concepts they present with relevant game mechanics and also lack the alignment

to educational frameworks.

The goal of this work is to create an educational resource that can teach students, aged 11-18, about various cybersecurity topics, providing them with a solid knowledge base that will better equip them for the cybersecurity-related challenges they may face throughout their lives. Moreover, a strong cybersecurity knowledge foundation amongst younger, pre-university level students allows them to potentially achieve higher levels of skill in later years as professionals. Furthermore, this resource empowers students to, directly or indirectly, spread the topics they have learned to those around them. This may include the teachers who incorporate the software into their teaching resources and the friends and family of students using it too, resulting in a safer online environment for both students and those in their social circles.

The main contribution of this work is the creation of a free-to-use website that hosts a collection of pedagogical games that are based on a UK government education framework titled "Education for a Connected World" [7]. The latter provided detailed guidance on the learning objectives in the area of cyber security that need to be incorporated into the teaching curricula of schools and colleges. Four games were created to cover the key topic areas detailed in these guidelines: **Password Blast**, **Network Tower Defence**, **Password Breaker** and **Secure.me**. To evaluate these games, two studies were conducted to collect feedback from the games' primary audience: students studying at secondary schools, sixth forms, and colleges.

The Technology Acceptance Model(TAM) was used to analyze user acceptance and usage of the games. The average Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness, and Intention to Use values were 4.08, 3.97 and 3.91 respectively. This demonstrated that on average, students found the game useful in their education, easy to use, and also intended to use the games in the future. The results also covered general positive feedback, which provided insight for future iterations.

The remaining sections of this paper are structured as follows. *Section 2 - Related Work* provides examples of existing cybersecurity games. *Section 3 - Design Methodology* describes how the games and the website were designed and the methods used. *Section 4 - Evaluation and Discussion* contains an evaluation of the created resource using two studies and the feedback collected from them. Finally, *Section 5 - Conclusion and Future Work* consists of the conclusion that can be drawn from this work and potential improvements.

2 Related Work

Previous research has demonstrated the impact of using serious cybersecurity games, including in sectors unrelated to cybersecurity. Min et al. found that the use of serious games within nursing aided and improved their knowledge and performance, and a literature review into serious games showed empirical evidence of the effectiveness of game-based learning [8][9]. This section provides a summary of key serious games currently available, in terms of design and educational goals.

Elevation of Privilege (EoP) is a card game based on the STRIDE threat model developed in 1999 by Loren Kohnfelder and Praerit Garg [10] [6]. The game aims to discover security vulnerabilities in a network model, which can be specific to the players. Each security category in STRIDE refers to a suit, and on each hand, a player must play a card from the current suit (if they have one). When playing a card, the player must read the card aloud, and demonstrate where they believe their threat card could take place on the network model. The winner of the hand is the card that has the highest number, referring to how severe the vulnerability is. The only exception is any card from the Elevation of Privilege suit, which will beat any card. Unfortunately, this game lacked proper evaluation, with little to no statistical evidence or results demonstrating its effectiveness. Shostack discussed a range of generally positive feedback received, ranging from students, state agencies, and local companies, however also admitted how these are difficult to document [6].

Riskio is a physical board game aiming to teach users different attacks, vulnerabilities and defences from university students to top-level staff [11]. It utilises playing cards and consists of a defence, attack, and discussion stage. The game requires an experienced cybersecurity expert to play as the Game Master and direct conversations. Players must attempt to defend an organisation from attacks, by considering the different attack vectors and methods that could be used to exploit the network. It is based upon the MOTENS model [12] and inspired by the Elevation of Privilege Card game. Evaluation using employee and student participants demonstrated that both groups perceived the game as effective in teaching, with employees having a higher confidence than students.

CyberCIEGE is a computer simulation game taking inspiration from Sim City [5]. The player is put into a virtual world and must operate to protect networks. The aim is to teach about vulnerabilities and how to prevent the possible

consequences that might occur. Scenarios can be created that the player must go through, with each scenario allowing for multiple phases and mini-objectives. These can be tailored specifically to a setting, as the threat and vulnerability landscape is far from linear. This game was created for use within different branches of the US Government, however can be accessed by any educational institution and can be used by any learning level. Limited evaluation based on feedback and review logs found the game to be educationally effective [13], and a further study that took place in a student security course showed the game generated more enthusiasm and was more popular than a video produced by the Department of Defence [14].

3 Design Methodology

This section discusses the existing approaches for serious game design and outlines the pedagogical principles adopted in this work. Additionally, an overview of the website designed to host the proposed game is provided.

3.1 Methods for Designing Serious Games

Three distinct game design models were considered as potential approaches for designing the games: the GOM (Game Object Model II) model, the LM-GM (Learning Mechanics – Game Mechanics) model, and the MOTENS model [15][16][12].

3.1.1 The GOM Model

The GOM model is based on object-oriented programming principles and breaks down the design problem into two parts [15]. It does this by assigning the learning objectives as “abstract interfaces” and the game mechanics as “concrete interfaces”. These interfaces are then assigned to objects, described as spaces, of which there are six types: Game Space, Visualisation Space, Elements Space, Actors Space, Problem Space and Social Space. The spaces can contain other objects within them, for example, the Elements Space encompasses the Actors Space, and, like the concept of inheritance in OOP, the ‘inner’ spaces contain all the interfaces of the ‘outer’(/parent) spaces. When using this model to create an educational game, the abstract interfaces refer to the educational elements within a specific space, whereas the concrete interfaces outline how these educational elements will

appear in the game mechanics and gameplay (see *Figure 1*).

3.1.2 The LM-GM Model

The LM-GM model aims to address the balance between educational and game-play aspects of games [16]. It introduces the concept of Serious Game Mechanics (SGM), which serves as the bridge between learning objectives and in-game mechanics. This model combines educational theories from the Learning Mechanics (LM) side and various game mechanic theories from the Game Mechanics (GM) side (see *Figure 2*).

In the central column of each Mechanics table, the model addresses the core concept. When compared with the corresponding position in the other mechanics table, it shows an equivalent concept. The boxes along the rows of each concept represent an array of mechanics that can be employed to reinforce it. To use this model for game development, a developer can, for instance, take a learning mechanic like “Question & Answer” and translate it into the game mechanic “Cascading Information,” which could incorporate cut scenes and a storyline.

3.1.3 The MOTENS Model

The MOTENS model, unlike the previously mentioned models, is specifically designed for educational cybersecurity games. It incorporates cognitive theory, learning objectives and game mechanics and allows them to be mapped to game elements with relative ease. The model splits the game design process into six high-level categories (see *Figure 3*):

An explanation of the concepts can be simplified to:

- Multiple Modes of Learning – Game mechanics should provide multiple different learning opportunities
- Ownership Self-Learning – Offer different game scenarios to achieve the learning objectives
- Theory – The educational theory behind the design
- Environment – Create gameplay in a suitable learning environment and game setting
- Negotiation - Changing the role from teacher to coach, not lecturing, and replacing content-delivery with problem-based learning

Figure 1: Game Object Model Version II Diagram

Figure 2: LM-GM Model Diagram

Figure 3: MOTENS Model High-level Categories

Table 1: MOTENS Model Stage 4 Design Steps

Design Steps	Description
Step 1	Initial Design Decisions
Step 2	Pre-Gameplay Processes
Step 3	Gameplay
Step 4	End-Of-Game Processes
Step 5	Review and Test Gameplay

- Self-Learning - The ability of the player to learn through problem-based learning, building on their knowledge [12]

The MOTENS model has a 5-stage process that results in the creation of a serious cybersecurity game. Within this process, Stage 4, designing the gameplay, is further divided into 5 steps with the final step involving testing and reviewing the gameplay, for example by collecting feedback from the primary target audience and improving the game based on said feedback (see *Table 1*). The game Riskio, among others, were created using this method [11].

3.1.4 Conclusion on Game Design Models

After reviewing the design methods, it was clear that the MOTENS model was the best choice for a base design model. It was chosen for its ability

to map learning objectives and game mechanics to game elements, while also incorporating cognitive theory, with relative ease. The step-by-step process for developing such games was another feature that made this model more suitable for this work than the others. Furthermore, the fact that MOTENS Stage 4 - Step 5 and Stage 5 both utilised iterative evaluation via user feedback collection also increased MOTENS's appeal as this meant that the games could be improved mid-design.

3.2 Game designs

This section explains the designs for each of the games. Each game was mapped to several learning objectives (LOs) developed from the initial list and the "Education for a Connected World" document [7]. Table 2 details the specific LOs as well as their corresponding topic area.

3.2.1 Development of Learning outcomes

Initially, a list of LOs was created that was mapped to the STRIDE threat model which categorised them into different sections [10]. To gain a better understanding of the requirements for these objectives, two playable game demos were created, with their game elements mapped to the first few items of the LO list. After these rudimentary demos were created and evaluated, it was clear that

the LOs needed to be updated before the actual games could be designed.

Many sources that could be used to make a more comprehensive list of LOs were considered, such as the National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC), the MITRE ATT&CK framework, and educational frameworks from UK examination boards such as AQA and Edexcel. Both the NCSC and MITRE ATT&CK websites contained highly relevant and important cybersecurity information, however, it was found to be difficult to extract game objectives from these websites. The exam board educational frameworks also were missing sufficient detail; they were too difficult or too vague to map to game mechanics.

A document titled “Education for a Connected World - 2020 Edition”, produced by the UK Council for Internet Safety [7], was deemed the most appropriate to use for the LOs. This document contained different topics ranging from general online safety to copyright and ownership, aimed at different age groups from 4 to 18 years, with the complexity and number of objectives increasing with each age group. This document provided a list of key objectives that someone of the age range must be able to achieve, providing guidance on how young people can safely use the internet. Eight main topics were discussed within this document. However, as the games focus on cybersecurity specifically, so, only the topics concerning privacy and security were used. These cover passwords, data management, network security, malware, and secure settings of browsers and apps. Within this document, many objectives overlapped with each other or were deemed too similar, hence a final list of learning objectives was created simplifying each of these five sub-topics. These are shown in Table 2.

3.2.2 Adapted Design Model Stages

The first stage of the MOTENS model requires the splitting up of players into gamers and non-gamers. However, feedback from an initial meeting with a partner school indicated that we should treat all players as non-gamers, removing the necessity to perform this step during the design process. For this reason, an adapted game design model was used, based on the MOTENS model, which omitted the first MOTENS stage as it did not apply to the planned work. A pictorial representation of this model can be seen in *Figure 4*. The rest of this section details the design stages undertaken to create the educational cyber security games.

Stage 1

There was an initial meeting with a partner school to gauge the school’s and students’ expectations, allowing for more informed early design and development.

Some key influences from this meeting included the decision to make multiple short games (approx. 10 minutes long) instead of a single larger game to allow them to be played during lessons while not taking up all of the lesson time. Also, it was decided that there would not be a game master in any of the games so students could be independent in their learning. Another decision was to host the games online rather than on local machines to allow students to play the games as homework / outside of a classroom lesson. Additionally, a decision was to include scores in the games as the students felt that this would encourage healthy competition between them, increasing their motivation to play the games and learn from them.

The LOs were then split up to be covered in 4 shorter online games. The Password Blast game incorporates LOs 1, 2 and 4 from the topic of passwords. Network Tower Defence focuses on the topics of network security and data management, covering LOs 13 to 18. From the topic of password security, Password Breaker maps to LOs 2, 3, and 5. Finally, Secure.me covers LOs 6 to 12 from the topics of secure settings of browsers and apps and malware awareness. The software chosen to create these games was the Unity¹ platform with the language C# used for scripting.

The core concept of Password Blast attempted to incorporate the style of classic rocket arcade games, giving the feeling of nostalgia and memorabilia. Inspiration was mostly taken from Space Invaders, where a rocket ship would shoot oncoming enemies. The design for Network Tower Defence incorporates the main aspects of a tower defence game. The player must try to defend the virtual network against multiple waves of enemies. The Password Breaker game was designed as a brick-breaker-style game with bricks representing passwords and password defences, and the ball and paddle representing an attacker and their password-cracking tools. It was decided that Secure.me would be split into 3 minigames, designed as variations of spot-the-difference puzzle games, where players would have to instead spot/identify game elements to complete the levels. The Secure.me minigames mimic real-life software, in the form of an internet browser, an email app, and an antivirus app.

Stage 2

¹<https://unity.com/>

Table 2: List of Learning Objectives

Topic	LO	Specific Objective
Passwords	1	Use simple strategies for creating and keeping passwords private
	2	Explain what a strong password is and demonstrates how to create one
	3	Manage passwords effectively
	4	Explain what to do if a password is shared, lost or stolen
	5	Explain the benefits of two-factor authentication and use it where available
Secure Settings of Browsers and Apps	6	Explain how many free apps or services may read and share private information (e.g. friends, contacts, likes, images, videos, voice, messages, geolocation) with others
	7	Demonstrate ways in which someone can change their browser settings to make their online browsing more secure (e.g. cookie permissions, do-not-track-me, password storage, incognito)
	8	Explain what cookies are and can give examples of how my online browsing can be tracked and used by others (e.g. adware)
	9	Explain app permissions and analyse them to make informed choices on which apps to use
Malware	10	Describe ways in which some online content targets people to gain money or information illegally and describe strategies to help me identify such content (e.g. scams, phishing)
	11	Explain what malware is and give some examples of how it operates and what the impact could be on a device or user (e.g. viruses, trojans, ransomware)
	12	Explain that accessing some websites or services may increase the risk of encountering viruses and other types of malware
Network Security	13	Explain the terms 'connectivity' and the 'Internet of things'
	14	Describe how connected devices can collect and share anyone's information with others, with or without their knowledge or awareness, e.g. device usage including microphone, camera and geolocation
	15	Explain why networks require secure management and can give examples of services that support this (e.g. firewalls, VPN, user monitoring)
	16	Explain how the security of data in a network can be compromised internally or externally and give examples of how this might occur (e.g. DDOS, proxy-bypass, distro, hacking). I can describe actions that can minimise risks
Data Management	17	Explain why backing up data is important and how this can be done
	18	Identify choices and demonstrate strategies to control the personal data online services hold

Figure 4: Design Process Diagram (Adapted from MOTENS Model [12])

The second stage of the adapted MOTENS model required a specific mapping of learning objectives to game mechanics. This was followed for all games, and can be seen in Tables 3 and 4. Following these principles ensures that the games contains the relevant aspects that contribute to learning, while balancing education and gameplay.

Stage 3

The design of the gameplay for each of the four games followed the step-by-step process detailed in *Figure 4*. *Table 6* shows how these stages are linked to these steps and the specifics of each game individually are discussed below.

Password Blast. This game comprises of a password creation scene and a rocket simulation scene. In the password creation scene, the user can add randomly generated words to a password string. They can also remove words or choose not to add words if they prefer another. The strength of the password they created would reflect the amount of fuel the rocket would start with. This is dynamically shown in the scene, by a fuel bar placed at the bottom. This bar level changes depending on how many words have been placed into the password string box. If it is three, then the maximum fuel will show. In the asteroid destruction scene, the player can control their spaceship and must shoot one of two asteroids containing a passphrase **not** created using the 3-word technique. Destroying the password not created using this technique, or the “incorrect” password would grant the user more fuel, and more points. Likewise, the oppo-

site would occur for destroying the correct password. The rocket ship also loses fuel at a constant rate over time. The player also loses fuel if they aren’t able to destroy a rocket before the asteroid hits the ship. This counts as destroying the “correct” asteroid (made with the three-word technique). Both sections aim to strengthen the MOTENS principle of replayability. As the password section uses words that are randomly generated from a predefined list, the password created would differ between playthroughs. This is also similar to the asteroid destruction scene, where the asteroid passphrases are randomly generated. The player would therefore get a slightly different experience every time they played.

The game uses a space theme, allowing the player to select a different graphic for the rocket. Also included are animations of the asteroids and projectiles, to increase the appeal.

Table 3: Password Blast & Network Tower Defence Game Mechanic Mapping

Key Idea	Design Mechanic	Examples in Password Blast	Examples in Network Tower Defense Game
Multiple Modes of Learning	Game Mechanics	In the asteroid shooting scene, the asteroids increase in speed resulting in a higher difficulty. The player is scored based on how long they survive through the asteroid belt. The longer they survive, the more points are given.	Game difficulty increases with each level. The higher levels are harder to beat due to more strategy required. The game also contains an endless mode.
Ownership of Self Learning	Different Game Scenarios	The two main scenes in the game are the password creation scene, and flying the rocket through the asteroid belt.	Each level introduces a new scenario to the player, depending on the threat they are facing. These scenarios are all under the premise that the player is a network administrator working within a school.
Theory	Learning Hierarchy	The base component skills of how to play the game are shown at the beginning of the game, and component skills relating to cybersecurity concepts are shown in the password creation scene.	The base component skills of how to play the game are shown at the beginning of the game, and component skills relating to cybersecurity concepts are shown in the scenario introduction of each level.
	Accountability vs Responsibility	The game rules and learning objectives are shown at the beginning of the game.	The game rules and learning objectives are shown per level.
	Self-Determination Theory	The game incorporates difficulty, defender roleplay and a rocket scenario.	The game incorporates difficulty, different levels, defender roleplay and scenario explanation.
Environment	Threat Modelling	The player is shown (through the fuel level) what passwords are strong and memorable and what passwords are not.	The player is shown how different threats can occur on a network and the different protections against them.
	Security Threats		
	Security Defences		
	Design & Graphics	High-quality pixel art style used.	
Negotiation	Role Play as defender	The player learns the 3-word technique for creating passwords.	The player learns different methods for protecting a network.
Self-Learning	Players current knowledge related to player's role	The game uses a trial and error method to figure out the 3-word technique. On later playthroughs, the player will subsequently build upon this information to achieve a higher score.	Level difficulty progression builds upon each level, requiring the player to use their prior knowledge. The player is given the role of a network admin defending against potential threats.
	Real-world problems	Passwords are used everywhere for accounts. This is a real-world problem that the player has to deal with and is therefore highly relevant.	Emphasis is placed on the importance of network protections and why they are required. This information is relevant to real-world cybersecurity threats.

Table 4: Password Breaker & Secure.me Game Mechanic Mapping

Key Idea	Design Mechanic	Examples in Password Breaker	Examples in Secure.me
Multiple Modes of Learning	Game Mechanics	The levels are gamified in increasing difficulty. This difficulty is determined by how many bricks are broken, with an additional multiplier that increases the score for consecutive brick breaks without ball hitting the paddle.	The game levels & minigames increase in difficulty; higher levels cannot be accessed without completing previous levels. Levels for the 1 st minigame have a countdown timer which rewards the player if they can complete the level quickly.
Ownership of Self-Learning	Different Game Scenarios	The player can play two different game modes: Normal or Endless, providing them with a varied gaming scenario of attacking a specific set of passwords and defences or an infinite set of them	Secure.me contains 3 different minigames that use varied game scenarios in the form of ‘programs’ that mirror real-life software which the player might use in their day-to-day lives.
Theory	Learning Hierarchy	The core topics for the game are gradually built upon, such that the easier concepts, like weak passwords, are delivered in the first few levels with more difficult concepts, e.g. password managers, introduced in later levels.	The minigames and levels are ordered in increasing concept difficulty, e.g. the topic of secure settings of browsers and apps is presented in the 1 st game and the harder concept of malware is presented in the 3 rd minigame.
	Accountability vs Responsibility	The game rules and objectives are described in-between each level. These descriptions are built upon each time so players must remember previous information or go back to revisit.	
	Self-Determination Theory	The game incorporates difficulty, attacker roleplay and a brute-force hacking scenario.	The game incorporates difficulty, multiple minigames, defender roleplay and scenario explanations.
Environment	Threat Modelling	The player is shown, through gameplay and information pages, different strength passwords, and what two-factor authentication and password managers are and how they work (high-level perspective).	The threats and defences are described to the player in between levels, and they then are shown how to secure browser and app settings, and various kinds of malware.
	Security Threats		
	Security Defences		
	Design & Graphics	High-quality open-source assets used.	
Negotiation	Role Play as attacker or defender	The player is presented with different strength passwords (easy, medium, hard) and protection mechanisms to attack.	The player is presented with different scenarios in which they must defend against data theft and malware attacks.
Self-Learning	Players’ current knowledge related to player’s role	The player must use their attacker knowledge of password strengths and protections to attack them correctly, e.g., stronger password bricks are harder to crack so take more attempts to do so.	As Secure.me mimics real-life software, players progressively learn how to defend themselves from attacks in scenarios they’re presented, with each attack building on the last.
	Real-world problems	Passwords are used every day in the real world. Learning how attackers try to crack passwords and their defenses is a relevant real-world problem.	Securely configuring browser and app settings and recognizing common types of malware are very important skills in real life, so learning how to do these things will help tackle real-world problems.

Network Tower Defence. For this tower-defence-style game, each tower is most effective against its enemy counterpart. For example, a DDoS enemy can only be effectively countered by a User Monitoring Tower. Each progressing level introduces a new network vulnerability and a corresponding protection/mitigation, detailed by information panels that describe the level scenarios. Table 5 shows the levels and their aspects. Each level has 3 waves, varying in how many enemies spawn. Each wave also has 3 phases, which is where enemies would spawn. A level would only have the enemies that were introduced in that level or previous levels. For example, Level 3 would contain the enemy-type ‘Phisher’ or ‘Man in the Middle’. When playing the game for the first time, the tutorial would explain to the user how to play the game, the basic concepts, and the objectives of it. Each tower has its own graphic, projectile, damage output, speed and range. These configurable settings differ between each tower. This aims to add to the replayability aspect of the MOTENS model as, if each tower was a replica of another with only a graphic change, this would severely impact the playability. Each level presents a different map, encouraging the player to think about tower positioning while playing. The only exception to this is the endless mode, which uses the same layout as the fifth and final level. The player is only given a single life, aiming to represent the danger of vulnerabilities. Although this may appear punishing, this meant careful balancing of levels was required.

There are two modes available to the user: Normal and Endless. In normal, the player progresses through a tutorial and each of the 5 levels, teaching different network attacks and mitigations. These levels are predefined, with the enemy waves being the exact same every time. In endless mode, the enemy waves are completely random and can last forever until the player dies.

The game was also designed in a manner that adding new levels, towers and threats would be of ease. Each part of the game is modularised as much as possible, meaning every entity could exist without any dependency on another. The map design for each level can also be easily adjusted, as these only require 2D vectors of corners for a path. A script specialises in generating and realising the tiles between each corner and producing a final enemy path.

The graphics use a network theme. Information panel backgrounds aim to display an image similar to the Windows 7 background (as if the player was a network administrator) and levels use a plain back-

Table 5: Attacks and Protections by Level

Level Number	Threat	Mitigation
Level 1	DDoS	User Monitoring
Level 2	MITM	VPN
Level 3	Phishing	IT Training
Level 4	Malware	Anti-virus
Level 5	Inside Man	Level Access

ground of tiles and vents. Each projectile, tower and enemy also has its own graphic, aiming to represent their respective entity.

Password Breaker. The gameplay for Password Breaker involves different levels where the attacker uses balls to break password bricks, mirroring brute-force attacks on password-protected systems. The game has three different ‘strength’ password bricks that metaphorise different levels of password strength. The bricks require a different number of hits from balls to break depending on their relative password strength. Two-factor authentication (2FA) bricks are introduced as an extra layer of protection for password bricks. The attacker/player has to crack a 2FA brick to reveal the password brick hidden underneath it. Password managers (PMs) are represented by large blue bricks that spawn a ‘firewall shield’ around them for 10 seconds after being hit by a ball, simulating the banning of suspicious IP addresses by password-managing system firewalls. When broken, PMs spawn additional balls, helping the attacker break any remaining password bricks in the level. This symbolizes the threat posed by a corrupted password manager as, in real life, this would reveal every password that a person stores in said PM, allowing the attacker to break into other accounts that person owns. Lastly, the game includes ‘firewall bricks’ that do not break when hit by a ball and act as a line of defence for the password and 2FA bricks, simulating firewalls blocking malicious requests to web servers.

Similarly to Network Tower Defence, Password Breaker also contains 2 game modes: Normal and Endless, linking to the MOTENS category of ‘Multiple Modes of Learning’. Normal mode contains 11 levels that the player can progress through, discovering new password bricks as they go. Endless mode utilises a Procedural Content Generation algorithm so every level/stage is generated at run time and is unique from any previous ones. Players face an infinite number of stages to clear until they lose all their lives. This provides a way for players to take responsibility for their learning as they can play endless new game scenarios to refresh their memories on the respective Password Breaker topics, linking to the MOTENS category of ‘Self-

Learning'. Additionally, game levels are locked until all previous ones have been completed, providing a clear way for the player to track their progression through the game and related cybersecurity topics. As its levels have the potential to contain every element of the game, Endless mode is unlocked last so the player already has experience with every game element (bricks) beforehand.

The game allows players to choose from three difficulty settings: easy, medium and hard. These affect the balls' velocities and the number of lives given to players at the start of levels, allowing both novice and experienced gamers to learn at their own pace. An in-game pause menu offers increased control and convenience to players, from which they can restart the level or navigate back to the main menu or the difficulty settings page. Also, a 'how to play' page at the start of the game explains the controls for any new players. Additionally, an experimental "developer mode" was added. This links the game to the type of account the player has on the website: a 'developer' or a 'standard' account. A request is sent to the website to get whether the user has a developer account, then, if so, a toggle button is displayed on the game's welcome page. If the toggle is selected, it enables the user to access all levels without requiring them to first be unlocked, simplifying game navigation and testing for those interested in the game from an academic or a developer perspective.

Secure.me. Due to its large set of learning objectives, Secure.me is divided into three distinct sections. Each section within Secure.me was designed to mimic the appearance of real-life software that players may experience in their day-to-day lives. The first section resembles an internet browser and contains a tutorial followed by 4 game levels that require players to identify pieces of information that may have been shared between two different 'websites'. Once players find this information, they can click on it, turning it yellow. Once the corresponding element in the other website, in the same level, is also selected both elements will then turn green. If an incorrect match is made, the elements will both flash red to show the user they have made a mistake.

The second section is modelled off an email app. Players have to look at a short list of emails and decide whether each one is malicious. There are indicators within 'malicious' emails that can be highlighted yellow by clicking on them, to assist players' learning. Once they are finished, the players can click a button called 'Check my answers!'. The game then displays to the user whether they have

successfully deduced the difference between the malicious and normal emails, as well as revealing any unhighlighted indicators in malicious emails and allowing them to retry the level if they failed.

The third section imitates an anti-virus software which has caught and listed some malicious programs. The player must go through each program and determine the type of malware used by each program based on information provided about them. Players can choose out of a virus, trojan, or ransomware for each program. Like the previous section, there is a 'check answers' button that shows the player their result and allows them to retry the level if they failed. After the first and final sections, players then take a quiz designed to reinforce and test their knowledge of the topics presented to them in the previous section(s).

Similarly to Password Breaker, the game levels in section 1 can be selected from a 'game levels' page, with the game levels locked until all previous levels have been completed, allowing for a gradual introduction of new game elements and pedagogical information. This applies to the latter sections too; section 1 must be completed before players can access sections 2 and 3.

Stage 4 Feedback from participants demonstrated that they found the games enjoyable to play and additionally commented on some potential improvements. These included making the games more difficult, adding more levels, or adding more features to improve gameplay. Results from the TAM model section showed that on average participants found the games useful to their education, easy to play and that they intended to use them in the future. In-depth results and details of this feedback can be found in Section 4.2.2.

Figure 5: Architecture of the *cyber-warriors.co.uk* website

Table 6: Design Stage 3 Steps for the Four Cybersecurity Games

Step	Description	Link to Password Blast	Link to Network Tower Defense	Link to Password Breaker	Link to Secure.me
1	Decide on the initial design	Rocket shooter game, inspired from Space Invaders. The player must destroy asteroids.	Tower defence game, with towers as protections and enemies as threats.	Brick-breaker game, with the attacker represented by a paddle, the method of attack (brute force) represented by the balls, and bricks representing vulnerabilities and defences.	Spot-the-similarities game consisting of three minigames. In the first, the player has to identify and decide if game elements represent shared user data, and in the latter two, decide if elements represent malicious programs.
2	Decide on the process before gameplay starts	Game contains an introduction and tutorial explaining the motivations and objectives.	Game contains an introduction and tutorial explaining the motivations and objectives.	Game contains a How-to-play page before gameplay is introduced as well as information pages informing players of levels' content and the reasoning behind them.	Players are introduced to the game via a tutorial level as well as information pages between levels.
3	Decide on the process during gameplay	In the first scene, the player must create a password. The strength and memorability decide the starting fuel. In the second scene, the player must shoot the asteroid with the password that wasn't made using the three-word technique to gain more fuel.	In each of the five levels, an introduction and scenario is given explaining the threat and protection.	All levels are prefaced with instruction/information pages which inform the player of the protection strategies available for passwords before they can play the level.	Players must locate relevant information within levels and make decisions, based on this and additional information provided to them via an in-game sidebar, to complete the game levels.
4	Decide on the process after gameplay	After the player completes the tutorial, their final score is shown. The player can play again to achieve a higher score.	The player must pass three waves of each level to move on to the next. Completion of the final level results in completing the game and unlocking endless mode.	All password bricks must be cracked and protection bricks avoided or broken before the levels can be completed. Completion of the final level in 'Normal Mode' unlocks 'Endless Mode' signalling the end of the game. Players can then replay any level or play 'Endless Mode'.	Two quizzes, after the first and last minigames, test what the player has learnt to reinforce the topics. After each minigame is completed, players can retry any of their previous levels. Once all 3 minigames are completed, the game ends by returning the user to the home page.
5	Test the gameplay	Games tested in a field study to collect feedback on their designs. See <i>Section 4.2.1</i> for more details			

3.3 Website Design

The website was designed in such a way that the content is dynamic, varying numbers of users can utilise the content and the website overall is easily maintainable. As such, the infrastructure used would be well-scalable to suit increasing levels of usage and storage needs, since the player base may grow over time, and more developers may upload their games onto the service. A preview of the website can be seen in Figures: 6 & 7. The front-end of the website was written using the React² framework and the MaterialUI³ component library. The back-end of the website was written using ExpressJS with Mongoose⁴, using a non-relational MongoDB database.

Figure 5 demonstrates the basis for the architecture used for the platform to run. Here, a simple document-style database storage was implemented for the metadata regarding users, game information, and other resources that may be stored on the service. The non-relational aspect of the database allows for very simple creating, reading, updating and deleting of resources, and high scalability. As Unity WebGL builds are likely to be of a higher storage capacity and harder to predict the size of, it was deemed more appropriate to dedicate a separate blob storage to these larger files.

The core of the app resides within the “back-end”, written in ExpressJS. It was separated from the “front-end” for two reasons:

- Separation of interests allows for easier management of both services,
- Reuse of the back-end opens up opportunities for the service to be used for means outside of the website front-end - for example, a supporting mobile app, or a developer API.

The back-end itself hosts the business logic - user management, data retrieval, permissions, etc. The front-end serves up the web page that the user sees and uses the information retrieved from the back-end within it. An online hosting service, Railway, is used that provides all of these services within one paid package.

3.3.1 Game hosting

Each game has its page displaying the playable version of the game, the title, the description, and other metadata. A system was implemented such

that the game is stored in the browser cache after the first time it is downloaded from the servers. The front end checks for a local version before requesting the build from the server again, resulting in decreased network usage to and from the server, and faster loading times for users.

Developers can easily edit and update their game builds and descriptions. This allows for improvements and new features to be added to the games rapidly. Given this, the version of the game is tracked internally on the servers and within the cached version of the game, such that if a user has an existing version of the game stored locally, but there is an updated version available on the server, then the new version gets retrieved and overwrites the existing build. This efficient system removes the stress of versioning from developers.

3.3.2 Scores system

Research suggests using gamification as a means of enhancing user engagement [17]. In particular, gamified learning environments improve student motivation, interest, and even score [18]. Similarly, social integration within these environments serves as a means of increased user retention, including competitive features [19].

One of the primary features of the website benefiting both developers and users is the integration of in-game scores with the website itself. Developers can use a dedicated API to interact with user accounts on the website, meaning that scores achieved by a player on a game can persist on the user’s profile and across login sessions. Having this information on the platform allows in-app leaderboards and scores to be displayed even outside of games. User profiles display high scores achieved by the user on each game that they have played, and accumulate a total “score” also displayed on the page. This total score contributes to the user’s position on the “global leaderboard”, which shows the highest-scoring users on the platform across all of the games hosted on it. Each game page has its own “game leaderboard”, which similarly shows the highest-scoring users on that game.

4 Evaluation and Discussion

As part of our adapted design model, two studies were conducted to evaluate the success of the games in terms of their design, appeal to the target audience, and educational abilities. This section details the designs of the two studies (*Section 4.1*), their results and the feedback received (*Section 4.2*), a comparison between the iterations (*Section 4.3*), a

²<https://react.dev/>

³<https://mui.com/>

⁴<https://www.mongodb.com/>

Figure 6: Cyber Warriors Website Description

Figure 7: Cyber Warriors Website Featured Games

comparison against existing cyber games (*Section 4.4*), and, finally, a reflection on the studies in general (*Section 4.5*).

4.1 Study Designs

The studies consisted of visits to partner schools to collect feedback from students about the mini-games and also to test how well they could teach cybersecurity topics. A range of students aged 11-18 were invited to participate through their tutors/teachers. On the day, the students were given a short presentation introducing the team members from the University and explaining the purpose of the study and what they could expect. The students then played the mini-games in their schools' computer rooms and filled out a questionnaire.

The second study was performed very similar to the first. It consisted of a short presentation, a pre-gameplay section of the questionnaire, some time spent playing the cyber games, and then a post-gameplay section of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was almost identical the same as the one used in the first study, which allowed for ease of comparison between the results. The only difference was that the knowledge test questions were not in a 'multiple-choice-single-answer' format, like in the first study, but were instead 'multiple-choice-multiple-answer'. This format was chosen to test the participants using a more difficult questioning style to see if they could recall, analyse and differ-

entiate between the content delivered to them instead of just identifying a single correct answer from amongst false ones. This upgraded the questionnaire from testing knowledge and recall (Bloom's first higher-order thinking skill) to testing comprehension (through translation) which is Bloom's second higher-order thinking skill, as students have to translate the questions and answers into familiar concepts to differentiate between all of the potential answers to find the correct ones [20].

4.2 Study Results and Feedback

4.2.1 First Study

The first iteration of the games consisted of 4 mini-games, which split up the different sub-topics mentioned earlier. These were then evaluated using a study as part of our Adapted Design Model Stage 3, Step 5: review and test gameplay. Ethical approval was gained for the study from the University of Southampton's Ethics and Research Governance (ERGO) system (ERGO/FEPS/78922 & ERGO/FEPS/78926). There were 41 participants in this study. The results and feedback from this study provided insight into what changes needed to be made to each game.

Results. Data from the first section of the questionnaire (see *Figure 8*) shows that the majority of participants answered 'Agree' or 'Strongly Agree' for most of the Initial Self-Evaluation questions, in-

dicating that they felt they already had some level of knowledge of the games' topics.

Results for the Knowledge Test can be found in Table 7. Questions concerning Password Breaker and Secure.me averaged a correct response of 72%, while questions about Password Blast and Network Tower Defence averaged 79%.

Participants appeared to struggle with answering Q8, which had to do with giving descriptions for "Connectivity" and the "Internet of Things". During this iteration, this information was shown after the tutorial, just before the game started. As some participants may have chosen to skip the tutorial, they may have thought that this information slide was part of it as well. Subsequently, this was moved to before the tutorial in the next iteration. Q2 was also difficult for participants. It asked participants to identify what private information could be shared between free apps and services. Only 4 of the 8 listed data types were included as game elements, with the other half presented to the user on an information page in between levels, which the users may have missed. This information was highlighted in red and had its text size increased in the next iteration of the game to better direct the players' attention.

The results of Section 3 for the TAM model can be seen in Figure 9. This section was based on the TAM Model and utilised a Likert scale for the answers [21]. The average value for Perceived Ease of Use was 4.18, Perceived Usefulness was 3.99 and Intention to Use was 4.07. These results show that participants above average found the games relatively easy to use (and play). This demonstrated that participants perceived the game as useful towards their education, easy to use and also had a positive intention to use the games in the future.

Feedback. Password Blast. Feedback from studies complained about a general lack of playability in Password Blast. Due to the second scene only being a simulation - in its purest form, the user was only clicking several buttons. Other feedback from the first study is shown below, indicating the changes needed to be made. This feedback showed that users:

- ... found the game lacked in replayability
- ... found the strength information was misleading
- ... found the repeating text parts were redundant
- ... found the user interface clunky
- ... thought the game was visually unappealing

- ... wanted to be able to type their own passwords
- ... wanted to be able to remove words from the password and see an indication of the wall strength
- ... wanted a multiplayer feature

This game required a heavy redesign, as core functions had negative feedback. Playability was a major issue, with participants complaining that they felt they were just clicking buttons and then watching a simulation. Better graphics and an updated user interface were also required to improve the aesthetic and appeal. A multiplayer feature was considered but not implemented, as the website would include a user leaderboard.

Network Tower Defence. For Network Tower Defence, constructive feedback requested for a general improvement in in-game functionality. This included feedback such as for the game to be more difficult, better graphics or better explanations. The comments outlined that users:

- ... were getting stuck on levels
- ... would like to progress through the game faster and learn quicker
- ... wanted to be able to sell towers
- ... wanted computer-related graphics
- ... found some levels repetitive
- ... found the tutorial boring and wordy

The main aspects to improve on were allowing for each level to contain multiple enemy types and the addition of an endless or infinite mode. Less important aspects such as graphical improvements or game features were also improved, however, had less of an effect on the final game.

Password Breaker. For Password Breaker, feedback suggested some improvements to the UI, such as the addition of a pause button, pause menu and 'How to Play' page, which were subsequently implemented. Some bugs identified by players in the studies were patched, like an issue with the ball velocity increasing when hit by player paddles at a certain angle. A home page was also added as well as a level-select page as users wanted to be able to retry specific game levels. Locking of levels was then implemented to maintain the linear progression of the games by preventing users from selecting levels based on educational topics they had not been introduced to. A common theme among the

Figure 8: Study 1 - Initial Self-Evaluation Section

- Q1 - I felt that I could learn at my own speed.
- Q2 - I felt the game was challenging enough.
- Q3 - I felt like I learned a new concept and that the game helped me to understand the topics better.
- Q4 - I would want to play this game again to learn more about the topics.
- Q5 - I enjoyed playing the game and would recommend it to others.

Figure 9: Study 1 - Section 3 (TAM) Results

feedback was that users wanted more game levels so several new levels were introduced as well as an 'Endless Mode'. Players commented that the game wasn't challenging enough so 'firewall brick' game elements and firewall shields around password managers were included in the update to increase the variation and challenge within the game. Difficulty settings were also added to allow for a more tailored gaming experience for each individual user.

Secure.me. Feedback about Secure.me indicated that it was initially unclear how to play the game. As such, the instructions within the tutorial level were improved, as well as the information displayed in the other levels, to increase the clarity on what was expected from the user. Furthermore, another improvement involved a visual indicator of incorrect matches, having the incorrectly matched game objects flash red. This improved clarity by providing immediate, in-game feedback to allow users to easily distinguish between successful and erroneous matches, without revealing too much about the other matches as the nature of the game involves players identifying unknown elements.

All Games. The major update to all of the games was moving them from being hosted on the free *itch.io*⁵ games platform to being hosted on the custom website <https://cyber-warriors.soton.ac.uk/>, to increase the inter-connectivity between them. The creation, and implementation within the games, of the website's API allowed the scores for each user to be sent to the website. The website then ranks the players based on their score for each game and displays a top-10 leaderboard on each game's web page, encouraging healthy competition amongst players to increase their motivation to play and also learn from the games [19].

4.2.2 Second Study

The second iterations of the games were also evaluated using a study as part of our Adapted Design Model Stage 4: Test the final design and evaluate the results. Ethical approval was gained from the University of Southampton's Ethics and Research Governance (ERGO) system (ERGO/FEPS/78922.A1 & ERGO/FEPS/78926.A1). This study involved 44 participants from the partner schools. The results and feedback from this second study provided insight into how well the games performed in terms of education and the TAM model metrics of PU, PEOU, and ITU.

Results. Data from the first section of the ques-

tionnaire (see *Figure 10*) again showed that the majority of participants answered 'Agree' or 'Strongly Agree' for most of the Initial Self-Evaluation questions. The next section of the questionnaire was the knowledge test and was to be completed after the participants had played the games on the website. For questions on the topics that the Password Breaker and Secure.me games covered (questions 1 to 7), the results were overwhelmingly positive, with an average of 64% correct answers across all participants for this section. Similarly, for questions concerning Password Blast and Network Tower Defence (questions 8 to 14), the results were 79%. The specific percentages for each question can be seen in *Table 7*.

Password Breaker & Secure.me: The two questions that received the lowest average score were questions 2 and 6. For question 2, 'Which of the following private information can free apps and services share?', the available answers were: *a. Phone contacts, likes, videos, geolocation, b. Voice recordings, friends list, private messages, c. All of the above.* The correct answer was 'c' but a significant 41% of participants chose 'a'. This was because within the Secure.me game, the elements listed in answer 'a' were demonstrated to the players visually within the game levels. The remaining items of private information that free websites and services share, listed in answer 'b', were included in an information page between two of the levels. This meant that those participants, who selected answer 'a', either skipped the page containing this information, did not read the content on it, or they did read it but could not remember this content.

The other question, 'Q6 - You come across an email that says you've won a free £10 voucher but you're not sure if it is a scam or genuine. Which of the following is NOT a method to help determine if the email is genuine?', had the lowest correct answer score out of all the questions - 27%. This can be attributed to the fact that it was the only trick question in the knowledge test section of the questionnaire. The possible answers to this question were: *a. Check if you have received an email from the same email address in the past, b. Check for any spelling mistakes in the email, c. Check if the language used in the email is time-sensitive / urgent.* The correct answer was 'a'. However, 49% of participants chose either one or both of the correct methods of determining a genuine email from a scam instead of the one incorrect method which was the right answer for the question. Excluding this question from the results, the average correct answer percentage for the study would have been 70% for

⁵<https://itch.io/>

this section, suggesting that this question itself may have been the source of error rather than the student’s learning capabilities.

Password Blast & Network Tower Defence: The lowest questions from 8-14 were questions 8 with 64% and question 10 with 52%. Results for Q8, which implemented the objective to do with defining “connectivity” and “Internet of Things”, suggest that the explanations given were not sufficient or memorable enough. The possible answers to this question were the following: *a. Connectivity: The number of cables and wires required to establish a stable connection between two or more devices. Internet of Things: A group of imaginary objects that exist virtually and have no physical presence or connection to the real world. b. Connectivity: The ability to connect systems or application programs. Internet of Things: Physical objects with sensors, processing ability and other technologies that connect and exchange data with other devices and systems over networks. c. Connectivity: The ability of a computer or device to generate and transmit electromagnetic waves to communicate with other devices wirelessly. Internet of Things: A virtual reality game that allows you to control physical objects in the real world.* The relevant information was shown in an information panel towards the very beginning of the game, even before the tutorial. It is possible that since this was not reinforced or commented upon again (as opposed to the network protections and vulnerabilities), students forgot the answer before they reached the questionnaire.

Q10 asked, “Which of the following examples support secure network management?”. The possible answers to this question were the following: *a. Installing more servers into the network. b. Using a firewall that is configured with factory settings c. Using a User Monitoring System.* A possible explanation for the low percentage of correct answers could be anchoring bias. This occurs when the respondent focuses too much on early information. In this case, it could mean participants failed to read or properly process the end of the statement, which mentions factory settings. This suggests that the low percentage was caused by question design as opposed to failing to learn this concept.

It should be noted that each information screen within Password Blast & Network Tower Defence contained a timer, which would count down from five or ten seconds depending on the content on the screen. It was therefore impossible for a student to skip this information, however, they could still choose to not look and ignore it if they wished.

Table 7: Correct Answer Percentages for Questions 1-14 of the Knowledge Test from Study 1 and 2

Question	1st Study (%)	2nd Study (%)
Q1 - What is the best way to make a secure password?	69	77
Q2 - Which of the following private information can free apps and services share?	54	52
Q3 - What method can be used to help prevent websites tracking you?	73	93
Q4 - What are cookies?	69	57
Q5 - You have found a calculator app online that can solve problems for you by scanning a page using the camera. Which of the following permissions should you allow for the app?	81	75
Q6 - You come across an email that says you’ve won a free £10 voucher but you’re not sure if it is a scam or genuine. Which of the following is <u>NOT</u> a method to help determine if the email is genuine?	73	27
Q7 - Which of the following effects will a virus have on a computer?	85	68
Q8 - What does “connectivity” and the “Internet of things” mean?	63	64
Q9 - What can be used on a device to collect and share information without the user’s knowledge or awareness?	90	88
Q10 - Which of the following examples support secure network management?	78	52
Q11 - Which of the following are examples of how a network can be compromised?	73	95
Q12 - Why is backing up data important?	93	93
Q13 - How can I control what information companies hold on me?	85	84
Q14 - Why are strong passwords required? And what’s one of the easiest ways to create them?	73	77

Feedback. The feedback from this study was overwhelmingly positive. Players indicated their willingness to play the games again in the future to remind themselves of the topics they learnt.

The final section of the questionnaire was about Gameplay and Self-Learning. The results from this section were also positive; the median response for each question was 'Agree'. The average values were 4.08 for Perceived Ease of Use, 3.97 for Perceived Usefulness and 3.91 for Intention to Use. This demonstrated that the participants perceived the games and website as useful to their learning and easy to use, and they expressed intention to use the product again in the future (see *Figure 11*). Overall, this indicated a positive acceptance rate among the students.

Most notably, the highest dimension was PEOU - for both studies 1 and 2. The results indicate that students generally had a positive perception of how easy it was to play the games and suggest that the games are highly beneficial in teaching cybersecurity concepts to students, especially from an engagement perspective. More games covering different or a wider range of topics could also cascade to the benefits of utilising this method of teaching.

Although the lowest metric out of the three was ITU at 3.91, this result still suggests a high likelihood of adoption and continued use of the games. ITU is directly influenced by PU and PEOU, which also had high averages. As students found the games both easy to use and useful towards their education, they are also more likely to intend to use them in the future.

At the end of this final section, there was a place where participants could write down any comments they had about the games, in terms of their educational or engagement characteristics. This feedback demonstrated a change of focus in student's comments between the first and second iterations of the games. While, after the first study, participants' feedback mainly related to larger issues with the games, such as a lack of playability and/or functionality, the majority of comments from the second iteration referred to minor details. For example, users commented on increasing the difficulty for the players who found the game easy, adding more game levels, and adding more game elements such as more types of bricks in the Password Breaker (PB) game.

On the other hand, one comment made a comparison between Network Tower Defence (NTD) and Password Breaker, saying that Password Breaker should explain the security concepts in more detail to the player, like NTD does, with information

pages in between levels. However, another comment asked for more content and information inside the actual game levels, rather than having players miss out on the information as they skipped all of the pages in between the levels.

From these comments, it was clear that the balance between placing information within the game levels versus outside of them is key to achieving maximum retention of information for all players, no matter their gaming ability. While the games were a success in educating players about the cyber security concepts they were teaching, improving the balance of the placement of valuable information would be a key aspect of any future improvements to the games.

4.3 Comparison of Study Iterations

In comparison with the results of the previous study's knowledge test (for PB and SM), participants in this study averaged 8% lower. The average mark for the previous study was 72% overall compared to 64% this time. When comparing the results of the previous study's knowledge test for Password Blast and Network Tower Defence, participants in this study averaged 12% lower. With 91% in the first and 79% in the second study respectively.

This could be attributed to the new format of questioning, multiple-choice-multiple-answer; this study aimed to push the participants' recall abilities and challenged them to use the higher-order thinking skill of comprehension [20].

The differences between Study 1 and 2 in Section 3 were minimal, with all values slightly decreasing from the first study. Intention to Use saw the largest decrease, from 4.07 to 3.90. The results could be explained through the initial questionnaire given before gameplay. In Study 1, the average participant agreed less towards the statements than in Study 2. This would explain why they could have found the games more useful than participants who were more originally confident. Overall, the differences between the two studies still show that, although changes were made to the games, participants perceived the games to be easy to use, useful for their education, and had the intention to play them in the future.

4.4 Comparison Against Serious Cybersecurity Games

When comparing to previous serious games mentioned in this paper, it is worth noting that the

Figure 10: Study 2 - Initial Self-Evaluation Section

- Q1 - I felt that I could learn at my own speed.
- Q2 - I felt the game was challenging enough.
- Q3 - I felt like I learned a new concept and that the game helped me to understand the topics better.
- Q4 - I would want to play this game again to learn more about the topics.
- Q5 - I enjoyed playing the game and would recommend it to others.

Figure 11: Study 2 - Section 3 (TAM) Results

series of games created are most similar to CyberCIEGE, due to the computer game nature. The issue with this game was the limited evaluation of feedback and review logs [5]. To not encounter the same issue, the games created were evaluated by the study that took place at two partner schools, in which students from ages 11-18 took part in playing the games and filling out the questionnaire. This provided valuable qualitative feedback that was used to address different educational and aesthetic issues within the game. Also, quantitative data from the adapted TAM section of the questionnaire allowed us to conduct further evaluation of the educational value.

Furthermore, the games also attempted to address issues presented by the Elevation of Privilege and Riskio card game. It can be argued that card games are far less popular and accessible as compared to online computer games. Although the feedback received for these card games was generally positive, it lacked proper evaluation. It can also be argued that the styles of both games cause a learning curve at the beginning of the game, due to each game respectively being a new card game. This was taken into consideration at the beginning of the project. By using old arcade-style themes, the games created could be said to invoke a sense of familiarity as opposed to players having to learn completely new mechanics.

4.5 Reflection

The questionnaire results aimed to allow comparisons between the studies and also provide insight into where improvements could be made. This was a mixed method providing qualitative (end-feedback) and quantitative data (section 3 - adapted TAM model). As the games were the first to use an educational framework as a basis, a questionnaire provided a suitable collection technique. Mean analysis was conducted on the quantitative data. The sample size was purely based on the availability of students from partner schools, and therefore there was limited control over this. However, there were a total of 85 participants across the two studies which is a sufficiently large sample size for evaluation of this work.

All game designs, original and updated, followed the adapted MOTENS model effectively to ensure that learning objectives map efficiently to game mechanics. Feedback from the first study provided suggestions for improvement, which also had to be incorporated using the MOTENS model. Using the model did not result in any design constraints, as features and mechanics were designed with the

model in mind. Additionally, original ideas could still be achieved, such as using game types familiar to a large audience (such as tower defence or brick breaker games). This therefore meant that creativity when developing the games was not restricted. The intention was for students to be able to play the games without teacher aid, so each game contains help screens aimed at supporting the student in case they become stuck.

As demonstrated by the results, the perceived learning value of playing games is high. Although it would be difficult to properly quantify this without conducting an A/B test where one group is taught using conventional teaching techniques and another group uses the game. The generally positive feedback received suggested that this form of gamification could be used as a suitable method to aid teaching, as opposed to fully replacing it. The style of learning also serves as a baseline for future serious games, demonstrating that this method is also effective for education. Another interest would be the retention factor and whether students would be able to remember concepts taught by the game at a later date. A further study would be required with the same students to establish this.

Each game can be said to meet the learning objectives taken from the educational framework. Since the MOTENS model was used (and adapted), this meant that each learning objective would have to be implemented as some form of mechanic, and would therefore be impossible to miss. The question would be how effective this mechanic is in implementing the objective, which is demonstrated by the results in Sections 2 and 3 of the questionnaires. Although games were not evaluated separately but rather in pairs, the results serve as a basis for future work and demonstrate the potential of creating games from educational frameworks.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This paper proposed a series of serious online cyber games: Password Blast, Network Tower Defence Password Breaker and Secure.me. These games covered the topics of password security, secure settings of browsers and apps, malware, network security and data management. The aim was to teach the cybersecurity concepts relating to these topics to students aged 11-18 through serious games as opposed to classic teaching methodologies. This further enhances young students' online security and, by extension, future organisations who may employ them.

The design model of the games was adapted from

the MOTENS model and was used to map the list of learning objectives, extracted from the Education for a Connected World document, to game mechanics within each game. The model ensured that the games stayed relevant to the learning objectives they aimed to teach. The first iterations of the games were evaluated through a study conducted at two local partner schools, following Stage 3, Step 5 ('Review and Test the Design') of the design model. Changes were then made to the games based on the feedback received. The final versions of the games were evaluated in the same way, following Stage 4 of the design model. Within the study, participants completed a self-evaluation questionnaire before playing the games, and a further questionnaire afterwards. This allowed analysis of how effective they were in teaching the concepts, and also how enjoyable they were to play, conducted through Section 3 of the questionnaire which was adapted from the TAM model.

A few issues were found in the evaluation of the final game versions. One issue was that some games were too easy, and students wanted more of a challenge. Another issue was that some students wanted more game levels or game elements. These comments were minor when compared to feedback received from the first iteration, where game concepts required major change. The final feedback suggested that an important balance between placing information inside versus outside game levels is paramount to ensuring player engagement and retention of information.

Future Work The website could be developed further to become an open-source platform, allowing other people to contribute games based on educational frameworks or similar guidance. This work could also be expanded to cover different levels of education by including games aimed at university students as well as those in Secondary School and 6th Form.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

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References

- [1] C. Group, "2022 cyberthreat defence report," CyberEdge Group, Tech. Rep., 2022.
- [2] Ipsos, *Cyber security skills in the uk labour market 2022 findings report*, Section 6 - Recruitment and skills shortages, Key Findings, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/cyber-security-skills-in-the-uk-labour-market-2022>.
- [3] H. Routledge, *Why Games are Good for Business*. Palgrave Macmillan, 2016.
- [4] S. Chauhan, "A meta-analysis of the impact of technology on learning effectiveness of elementary students," *Section 3.2, Computers and Education*, 105, 14–30, 2017. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2016.11.005>.
- [5] Naval Postgraduate School, "CyberCIEGE". [Online]. Available: <https://nps.edu/web/c3o/cyberciege>, (accessed: 23.09.2023).
- [6] A. Shostack, "Elevation of privilege: Drawing developers into threat modeling," in *2014 USENIX Summit on Gaming, Games, and Gamification in Security Education (3GSE 14)*, 2014.
- [7] U. C. for Internet Safety, "Education for a connected world - 2020 edition," UK Council for Internet Safety, Tech. Rep., 2020. [Online]. Available: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/896323/UKCIS_Education_for_a_Connected_World_.pdf.

- [8] A. Min, H. Min, and S. Kim, "Effectiveness of serious games in nurse education: A systematic review," *Nurse Education Today*, vol. 108, p. 105178, Jan. 2022, issn: 02606917. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2021.105178.
- [9] T. M. Connolly, E. A. Boyle, E. MacArthur, T. Hainey, and J. M. Boyle, "A systematic literature review of empirical evidence on computer games and serious games," *Computers & Education*, vol. 59, pp. 661–686, 2 Sep. 2012, issn: 0360-1315. doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2012.03.004.
- [10] A. Shostack, *Threat Modeling: Designing for Security*. Wiley, 2014.
- [11] S. Hart, A. Margheri, F. Paci, and V. Sassone, "Riskio: A serious game for cyber security awareness and education," *Computers and Security*, vol. 95, 2020, issn: 01674048. doi: 10.1016/j.cose.2020.101827.
- [12] S. Hart, B. Halak, and V. Sassone, "Motens: A pedagogical design model for serious cyber games," *arXiv:2110.11765 [cs.CR]*, 2021.
- [13] M. Thompson and C. Irvine, "Active learning with the cybercieve video game," in *Proceedings of the 4th Conference on Cyber Security Experimentation and Test*, ser. CSET'11, San Francisco, CA: USENIX Association, 2011, p. 10.
- [14] J. Jones, X. Yuan, E. Carr, and H. Yu, "A comparative study of cybercieve game and department of defense information assurance awareness video," in *Proceedings of the IEEE SoutheastCon 2010 (SoutheastCon)*, 2010, pp. 176–180. doi: 10.1109/SECON.2010.5453895.
- [15] A. Amory, "Game object model version ii: A theoretical framework for educational game development," *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 55(1), 2007.
- [16] S. Arnab, T. Lim, M. B. Carvalho, *et al.*, "Mapping learning and game mechanics for serious games analysis," *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 46(2), 2014.
- [17] S. Deterding, M. Sicart, L. N. K. O'Hara, and D. Dixon, "Gamification. using game-design elements in non-gaming contexts," *CHI EA '11: CHI '11 Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2011.
- [18] G. Barata, S. Gama, J. Jorge, and D. Goncalves, "Improving participation and learning with gamification," *Gamification '13: Proceedings of the First International Conference on Gameful Design, Research, and Applications*, 2013.
- [19] L. K. Kaye and J. Bryce, "Putting the "fun factor" into gaming: The influence of social contexts on experiences of playing videogames," *International Journal of Internet Science*, 7(1), 2012.
- [20] B. S. Bloom, M. D. Engelhart, E. J. Furst, and D. R. Krathwohl, *Taxonomy of educational objectives the classification of educational goals handbook 1 cognitive domain longmans*, 1956.
- [21] A. Yusoff, R. Crowder, and L. Gilbert, "Validation of serious games attributes using the technology acceptance model," *Second International Conference on Games and Virtual Worlds for Serious Applications*, 2010.